

**‘Between the Generations’:
Digital Immigrants/ Visitors versus Digital Natives /Residents**

Dr. Sharad K. Binnor
Head, Dept. of English,
K. K. Wagh Arts, Sci. & Com. College, Pimpalgaon (B),
Tal. Niphad, Dist. Nashik, Maharashtra
Affiliation: Savitribai Phule Pune University, Pune
sharadbinnor@gmail.com
+919850100253

Abstract

Interactions between teacher and students have changed radically with the advent of globalization and technological revolution. Students born in the digital age are well tuned with technology and new communication technology. They are no longer the students our education system was designed to instruct. They are ‘Digital Natives’¹ (Prensky) or ‘Residents’² (White) who detest slow, step-by-step, lecture oriented and serious instruction. Teachers are not so techno-savvy and well adapt with the technology. They are ‘Digital Immigrants’¹ (Prensky) or Visitors² (White) who are still suspicious of the technology and its utility in the classroom. The present paper tries to discuss the interactions between these two people belonging to different generations, the difficulties they face and possible solutions to bridge this generation gap by comparing the typologies introduced by Marc Prensky and David White.

Keywords: Globalization, Digital Natives and Digital Immigrants, communication, interaction, Visitors, Residents.

1

The first impact of Globalization was observed in the field of education. It has also brought tremendous changes in the implications of language teaching and learning. It brought into focus a need to develop the ‘Global language’, a language that can cater to the communicative needs of people all over the world. The hangover of colonialism compelled us to

choose English to serve this purpose. Besides, a systematic project was initiated by America and England to promote English as language of the world through diplomacy. Towards the end of the 20th century English became a truly global language and since then it has kept its privileged position among other world languages. It has become the language of all world business transactions. As a result, ELT business flourished in countries where it is being taught as second language or foreign language. According to the recent estimates, more than two billion people all over the world speak English. English has become either a compulsory or optional subject in school as well as university curricula. Being a global language, English serves different functions, in the Inner Circle countries, to use Kachru's terminology (Kachru & Nelson: 2001), it is the first language. In two outer circles; firstly in India, Pakistan, China, Japan and Nigeria, English is used as a second language together with other languages as a means of communication and; secondly in unspecified number of countries, it is taught as a foreign language in schools and universities.

Earlier English studies were restricted to inculcating the skills of literary and critical appreciation of literary texts. And whatever language study initiated was more or so focused on the historical or comparative study of language(s). The synchronic study of language was undertaken with the development of Saussurean linguistics. Globalization and technological revolution towards the end of the twentieth century further changed the goals and methods of English language studies. For example, the transfer of huge database of lexicon in Oxford English Dictionary onto a CDROM. Now the whole history of origin of any word is just a click away. Technology has helped us undertake research in the field of auditory, acoustic and articulatory phonetics. The development in technology has put newer hurdles before the teacher; he is beset with 'insistent demands of improving communicative ability of his students and simultaneously to face up to a technological computer-dominated future' (Andrew Goddwyn: xii). To use Marc Prensky's typology, the teacher is a 'digital immigrant' interacting with the 'digital natives' i.e. students (1).

Interaction between the English teacher and students is a kind of mediation. The teacher functions as a mediator of both global language and culture. S/he promises global citizenship to his or her students by exposing them to English language and culture of English. S/he facilitates their communication ability across intranational and international boundaries. With the advent of

globalization and technological revolution towards the end of the twentieth century, this interaction has undergone a tremendous change. Students are exposed to global language and culture through other media such as internet. They have become habitual to the speed, multimedial aspects and vastness of this media. Hence, teachers who were not born in this digital age have to learn new ways to interact with the present generation of students. In the coming pages, I am going to discuss the changed relation and interactions between teachers and students by using typologies introduced by Marc Prensky and David S. Whit.

2

There is a remarkable change in today's students; they are no longer students our education system was designed to instruct. They represent the first generation that grew up with this new technology. Throughout their lives, they have used or are surrounded by all sorts of digital or technological gadgets. To Marc Prensky, 'Today's average college grads have spent less than 5,000 hours of their lives reading, but over 10,000 hours playing video games (not to mention 20,000 hours watching TV). Computer games, email, the Internet, cell phones and instant messaging are integral parts of their lives' (Digital Natives: 1). Their ways of process information are different from their predecessors. Their brains have not changed physically but their thinking patterns have certainly undergone some changes. Prensky coined a term, 'digital natives' to refer to the present generation of students (ibid). They are 'native speakers' or 'native users' of digital language that overshadows all communication media these days.

Teachers who were not born in the digital age (though some young teachers were) are, according to Prensky, 'digital immigrants' (2). They are afraid of or fascinated by this technology; most of them are adopting the technology as there is no other option while there are still who detest its use and have fears of losing their influence in the classroom. Prensky observes that though teachers are adapting to the conditions of digital age, they still retain their strong belief in the age-old, traditional, time-tested approaches and techniques. He comments:

As Digital Immigrants learn – like all immigrants, some better than others – to adapt to their environment, they always retain, to some degree, their "accent," that is, their foot in the past. The "digital immigrant accent" can be seen in such things as turning to the Internet for information second rather than first, or in reading the manual for a program rather than assuming that the program itself will teach us to use it (2).

He cites some examples to signify this ‘accent’; this generation of teachers ask for print outs or hard copies, need prints to edit matter instead of editing it on the screen, show the interesting or useful website to others instead of sending just the URL, and enquire the receiver whether s/he has got their email by calling. He wants them to shrug off these habits and learn a new language (leaving behind their ‘pre-digital’ language) to instruct students who learn faster when digital components are incorporated in the classroom. While citing the different styles and needs of the digital native community, he says:

Digital Natives are used to receiving information really fast. They like to parallel process and multi-task. They prefer their graphics *before* their text rather than the opposite. They prefer random access (like hypertext). They function best when networked. They thrive on instant gratification and frequent rewards. They prefer games to “serious” work (2).

So the interactions between ‘digital natives’ and ‘digital immigrants’ are not effective as the later do not appreciate the styles and skills of the former and continue to teach ‘slowly, step-by-step, one thing at a time, individually, and above all, seriously’ (2).

To Prensky, digital immigrants don’t think that students can learn effectively while ‘watching TV or listening to music’ as they cannot do so. To them, learning can never be fun. They don’t understand that students are habitual to speed of the net, video games, instant downloading, online resources, quick messaging and have a little patience for slow and step-by-step lecturing. As a result, students have to ‘power down’ or choose not to pay attention in the class. Teachers think that students have not changed and they could continue to instruct in the same way as they were taught by their teachers. Unfortunately this immigrant/native divide is widening leading to students not attending classes and instead spending more time online with PCs, laptops, tablets, smart-phones etc.

Prensky asks two relevant questions: ‘should the Digital Native students learn the old ways, or should their Digital Immigrant educators learn the new?’ (3) He thinks that Digital Native students will never adopt the old ways and it is very demanding on the part of the Digital Immigrants to master the new. Therefore, he demands a total revamp of our methodology and content. Regarding the methodology, he argues:

Today’s teachers have to learn to communicate in the language and style of their students. This *doesn’t* mean changing the meaning of what is important, or of

good thinking skills. But it *does* mean going faster, less step-by step, more in parallel, with more random access, among other things (4).

He distinguishes between two types of content viz. legacy and future content. He derives the term legacy from computer, meaning ‘old system’. Legacy content consists of reading, writing, arithmetic, logical thinking, historical studies and all the traditional curricula. This content, according to Prensky, is important but it is for different era. Some of it is still relevant but most of it is unnecessary.

Future content, on the other hand, is digital and technological; it involves software, hardware, nanotechnology, genomics etc. It also includes humanities such as politics, language, history etc. This content is found interesting and engaging by the Digital Natives. However, teachers are not able to incorporate the future content in the traditional content. Learning the new ways to learn old as well as new stuff is the need of an hour. It is high time that teachers should invent new methodologies, taking cues from the Digital Natives, to make their instruction effective and compatible with the present generation. Finally, Prensky advocates the Digital Immigrant teacher community and ask them to change themselves and adopt the new ways to reach the Digital Natives.

3

David S. White uses ‘visitors’ and ‘residents’ for Prensky’s ‘Digital Immigrants and Digital Natives’ respectively. He challenges the basic premise on which Prensky’s typology is based. His Visitors/Residents continuum explains behaviour of people in different ways in using technology, depending on their motivation and context, without classifying them according to age or background. To him, Prensky’s typology is long dead, redundant and irrelevant. Hence, he comes up with an alternative typology to account for proper analysis of online behaviour of teachers and students. His objection to Prensky is in regard to the connection he established between computer competency and age. So he questions the hypothesis that the old generation is handicapped so far as use of technology for instruction is concerned and the present generation is privileged as they are born in digital age. He cites Margaryan and Littlejohn who argue:

Many young students are far from being the epitomic global, connected, socially networked technologically-fluent digital native who has little patience for passive and linear forms of learning. While the use of technologies is limited in terms of the range and the nature, there is some evidence that younger students use some tools more actively than the older students, but neither of these two groups uses these technologies to support their learning effectively. Educators therefore

cannot presume that all young students are “digital natives” who understand how to use technology to support and enhance their learning (cited in Visitors and Residents: 4).

He also rejects Prensky as his thesis predates the launching of social media which has changed the way we use internet or computer-mediated communication. And it has put ‘place’ at the centre stage. Hence, he uses ‘visitors’ and ‘residents’ as a new distinction instead of ‘digital natives’ and ‘digital immigrants’. To him, ‘place’ does not just mean virtual or physical place but a ‘sense of being present with others’. Earlier internet was used only for the purpose of finding information. But with the arrival of social media since 2003, internet is used to build community network and project oneself online through various social media tools. He writes:

Prior to 2003, the Internet was used primarily as a means of finding information with Google leading the way since 1997 in offering an effective means of searching for and gathering information. A key distinction between information-gathering versus social-networking sites is that the latter invite individuals to project their personas online as a ‘digital identity’ via text, image and video. Furthermore, social media platforms facilitate the construction, by the individual, of complex social networks not constrained by physical geography (6).

He, then, goes on to describe the ‘visitors’ and ‘residents’ continuum. The features of the ‘Visitors’ are:

- They consider ‘web’ as an untidy place to be visited to complete a certain task.
- They don’t have their persistent personal profile online to project their individual identity into the digital space.
- For them, issues of privacy and fear of identity theft are paramount.
- They have negative about social media and consider it as banal and egotistical.
- They are not averse to use email or Skype for communication but are wary of creating a Facebook profile.
- To them, web is just a kind of another tool that they can use for achieving certain goals.
- They are actually thinking off-line. Hence, they are users but not members of the web (8-9).

On the contrary, the ‘Residents’ are:

- They view web as a place where they live, interact and share information with other ‘residents’.

- A proportion of their lives is actually lived out online where the distinction between online and off–line is increasingly blurred.
- Residents are happy to go online simply to spend time with others and they are likely to consider that they ‘belong’ to a community which is located in the virtual.
- They have a profile in social networking platforms such as Facebook or Twitter and are comfortable expressing their persona in these online spaces.
- To Residents, the Web is a place to express opinions, a place in which relationships can be formed and extended. While they use ‘tools’ such as online banking and shopping systems they also use the Web to maintain and develop a digital identity.
- Since they also undertake many of the activities that Visitors do, their residency is an additional layer of interaction and activity.
- When Residents log off, an aspect of their persona remains. This could be in many forms ranging from status updates to social networking platforms, to artefacts in media sharing sites or opinions expressed in blog posts or blog comments.
- They see the Web primarily as a network of individuals or clusters of individuals who in turn generate content. Value online is assessed in terms of relationships as well as knowledge.
- They do not make a clear distinction between concepts of content and of persona. A blog post is as much an expression of identity as it is a discussion of particular ideas. The fact that Wikipedia has been authored collectively is not a concern, what is important is how relevant the information they find is to their particular needs (9).

To White, his typology is a continuum not a binary opposition. We can place ourselves at a particular point ‘along this continuum rather than in one of the boxes’ (9). So also, he does not consider the ‘Visitors’ as less competent digitally as compared to the ‘Residents’. His paradigm of Visitors/Residents is more useful in describing the practice of technological engagement than Prensky’s Digital Immigrants/Digital Natives.

The implication of this discussion of Prensky's Digital Immigrants/Digital Natives and White's Visitors/Residents continuum are that with globalization and technological revolution the relation, styles and language of teachers and students have radically changed and there is need to evolve a different methodology and content to cater to the needs of students who have digital DNA. Prensky's ideas are quite predictive and insightful though some of them are debatable. It is not just about how tech-impaired we, the teachers, are; but also about how we deal with the world views that accompany these technologies. I think Prensky's observations are quite relevant in an urbanized context, where kids are born with tech-tuned DNA, and grow up with smart technologies around them. But his views might sound little out of place, even ridiculous, in a third world rural context.

Notes:

1. Marc Prensky coined the terms 'Digital Natives' and 'Digital Immigrants' to refer to today's students and teachers respectively in his 2001 essay *Digital Natives, Digital Immigrants*, in *On the Horizon* Vol. 9 No. 5. 2001.
2. David S. White provides alternative typology of Visitors/Residents to replace Prensky's 'Digital Immigrants' and 'Digital Natives' in his *Visitors and Residents: A New Typology for Online Engagement* in *First Monday* Vo. 16 No. 9. 2011.

Bibliography:

1. Andrew Goddwyn ed. *from* Introduction. *English in the Digital Age*. New York: Cassell. 2000. Print.
2. Kachru, B.B., & Nelson, C.L. World Englishes. In A. Burns, & C. Coffin (Eds.), *Analysing English in a global context* (pp. 9-25). London and New York: Routledge. 2001. Print.
3. Prensky, Marc. *Digital Natives, Digital Immigrants*, in *On the Horizon* Vol. 9 No. 5. 2001. Web. URL. <http://www.marcprensky.com/writing/Prensky%20-%20Digital%20Natives>
4. White, David S. *Visitors and Residents: A New Typology for Online Engagement* in *First Monday* Vo. 16 No. 9. 2011. Web. URL. www.firstmondy.org/article/view/3171/3049